

Influence of a bio-based fertilizer on pharmaceuticals uptake by wheatgrass in soil

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ARTICLE INFO

Edited by Dr Hyo-Bang Moon

Keywords:

Pharmaceuticals
Bio-based fertilizers
Uptake
Bioaccumulation concentration factor
Soil pore water

ABSTRACT

Establishing linear or nonlinear relationships for the uptake of both neutral and ionized pharmaceuticals by crops with key parameters is crucial for understanding the variations in uptake behavior among pharmaceuticals, yet it remains highly challenging. In this study, greenhouse experiments were conducted using wheatgrass (*Triticum aestivum*) grown in Finnish soil without (FS) and with a BBF (FO), spiked with seventeen neutral and ionized pharmaceuticals, to explore these relationships and investigate the impact of BBFs on their uptake. For the first time, a linear model revealed a significant correlation between BCF_{spw} (bioaccumulation concentration factors based on soil pore water) and both half-life and solid-water distribution coefficients (K_d) of studied pharmaceuticals in soil. The correlation varied between compounds with short half-lives (<14 days; $R^2=0.73$) and those with long half-lives (>14 days; $R^2=0.70$). The coefficient ratios of K_d to half-life in the model were 3.4 and 14.7 (g/ml)-day for compounds with long and short half-lives, respectively, suggesting a predominant influence of sorption of compounds on their bioaccumulation in wheatgrass compared to persistence. BBF significantly enhanced their sorption, thereby reducing pharmaceutical uptake by plants despite increased persistence. These findings suggest BBFs may be a promising tool to mitigate pharmaceutical accumulation in crops.

1. Introduction

In modern agriculture, there is an increasing trend towards replacing chemical fertilizers with organic or bio-based fertilizers (BBFs) to enhance soil fertility and increase crop yields (Chojnacka et al., 2020). However, these practices raise concerns about potential alterations of soil characteristics, such as an increase in soil organic matter content. BBFs can slow down the dissipation of pharmaceuticals in soil (Prosser et al., 2014; Sabourin et al., 2012; Williams et al., 2015; Winker et al., 2010), increasing the duration of pharmaceutical exposure to plant roots and thus the potential for bioaccumulation. Simultaneously, BBFs may cause an increase in sorption affinity of the soil (Prosser et al., 2014; Sabourin et al., 2012; Williams et al., 2015; Winker et al., 2010), which

may reduce the bioavailability of pharmaceuticals, consequently decreasing their potential for bioaccumulation. As a result, the overall impact of BBFs on the bioaccumulation of pharmaceuticals in crops grown on soils on which they are applied remains unclear, as these factors could either promote or inhibit the uptake process.

Extensive research has been conducted on the uptake of pharmaceuticals by crops, indicating that this process is significantly influenced by the chemical properties of the compounds (Herklotz et al., 2010; Li et al., 2022; Liu et al., 2021; Wu et al., 2013). For example, carbamazepine, characterized by its high lipophilicity (log P (octanol-water partition coefficient) = 2.45), tends to accumulate in high concentrations in crops (Li et al., 2020, 2022). The root concentration factor (RCF) is instrumental in assessing the potential for pharmaceutical uptake by

Abbreviations: BBFs, Bio-based fertilizers; FS, Finnish soil; FO, Finnish soil with BBF amendment; BCF_{spw} , ml/g, Bioaccumulation concentration factor based on soil pore water; Log P, Octanol-water partition coefficients; Log D, pH-dependent octanol-water partition coefficients; K_d , ml/g, Solid-water distribution coefficient; BCF, Bioaccumulation concentration factor; SPW, Soil pore water; IS, Labelled standards; TES, Total extractable fraction; MeOH, Methanol; ACN, Acetonitrile; SRE, Spiked recovery experiments; ME, Matrix effect; MLOD, Method limit of detection; MLOQ, Method limit of quantification; RSD, Relative standard deviation; Ct, ng/g, Concentration at time t day; C_0 , Initial concentration at $t = 0$; k, day^{-1} , First-order dissipation rate constant; C_s , Concentration in soil; C_{spw} , ng/ml, Concentration in soil pore water; BCF_s , ng/g, Bioaccumulation concentration factor based on soil; $t_{1/2}$, day, Half-life; EDI, ng/g bw/day, Estimated daily intake HQ, dimensionless, Harzard quotient; ADI, ng/g bw/day, Acceptable daily intake; IR, g/day, Ingestion rate; BW, kg, Body weight; MRL, Maximum residue limit.

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2025.119313>

Received 28 April 2025; Received in revised form 16 October 2025; Accepted 26 October 2025

Available online 31 October 2025

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crops, showing a positive correlation with log P or log D (pH-dependent octanol-water partition coefficient) for neutral pharmaceuticals (Miller et al., 2016). Additionally, ionized compounds are also capable of migrating through roots to accumulate in plant tissues in soil (Li et al., 2022). For instance, significant concentrations of ionized diclofenac, sulfamethoxazole, and trimethoprim (3.4–12.63 ng/g) have been detected in tomato fruits grown in soil irrigated with municipal wastewater (Christou et al., 2017a). However, in recent decades, the relationship between the RCF and log P or log D for ionized compounds is statistically poor (e.g., $R^2 < 0.4$) (Chuang et al., 2019; Li et al., 2022; Miller et al., 2016). In addition, BBFs do not affect the log P or log D (when pH in BBFs is the same as soil) of compounds in soil, which means that the effects of BBF application cannot be assessed by these parameters. By establishing appropriate relationships between the concentration factors of both neutral and ionized compounds with key parameters, it becomes easier to comprehend their uptake behavior by crops in both soil and amended soil.

The bioavailability of pharmaceuticals for plant uptake is predominantly determined by their presence in soil pore water (SPW) (Carter et al., 2015; Li et al., 2022). This suggests that roots may directly absorb pharmaceuticals more readily from SPW than from the bulk soil. Notably, the concentration dynamics of each pharmaceutical in SPW correlate well with the RCF among soils (Li et al., 2020, 2022). Thus, examining the interrelationships among different pharmaceutical compounds in SPW in terms of their concentration factors is pivotal. Concentration dynamics in SPW do not always adhere to a specific model, such as the single first-order model, complicating the establishment of a direct link between parameters in SPW and the RCF (Carter et al., 2014). Concentrations of pharmaceuticals in SPW can be quantified as the ratio of their concentration in the soil to their sorption affinity as expressed by their solid-water distribution coefficient (K_d) values. This relationship allows for the exploration of the interplay of the half-life of pharmaceuticals in soil, their K_d values, and their concentration factors. BBFs might influence the concentration dynamics of pharmaceuticals in SPW, subsequently affecting their bioaccumulation in soils. Consequently, we hypothesize that there is a strong correlation between K_d values, half-life in soil, and the concentration factors of the compounds. Moreover, BBFs may influence the uptake behavior of these compounds in amended soil by altering these two key factors. To our knowledge, this is the first model to couple K_d and half-life to predict concentration factors for both neutral and ionized pharmaceuticals in soils.

To verify our hypothesis, we conducted greenhouse experiments using a Finnish agricultural soil with and without BBF amendment and spiked with 17 pharmaceutical compounds spanning neutral, cationic, and anionic species and wide ranges of soil persistence and sorption potential in soil. On this soil, wheatgrass (*Triticum aestivum*) was grown as a model plant in light of its rapid growth cycle and widespread cultivation.

2. Materials and method

2.1. Materials

LC-grade solvents methanol (MeOH) and acetonitrile (ACN) were supplied by Biosolve (Valkenswaard, The Netherlands). Formic acid and acetic acid were purchased from Merck (Damstadt, Germany). Single distilled (demi) water was further purified with an ELGA water purification system (Veolia Water Technologies, Ede, the Netherlands); we subsequently refer to this as double distilled water.

Analytical grade standards of 17 pharmaceuticals and 11 isotopically labelled standards (IS) used for quantification were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. These compounds are frequently detected in soils at ng/g levels, are widely used in greenhouse experiments, and commonly serve as model substances (Camacho-Arévalo et al., 2021; Christou et al., 2017; De Mastro et al., 2024; González-Naranjo et al., 2013; Knight et al., 2018; Sleight et al., 2023). Detailed information is provided in

Table S1 in Supporting Information.

The soil used in this study was collected from a field site in Finland that is part of the field trials of the LEX4BIO project that aims to close nutrient cycles in Europe and diminish the environmental impact associated with traditional fertilization methods and is further described in (Das et al., 2023). Previous studies have demonstrated that the bioaccumulation of pharmaceuticals in crops is primarily influenced by soil organic matter (Ben Mordechay et al., 2018; de Boer et al., 2018). Therefore, a commonly used BBF, **OG2**, was selected for this study. **OG2** is derived from animal by-products and is notably rich in organic matter (Das et al., 2023). The soil characteristics determined in the present study are shown in Table S6.

2.2. Greenhouse experiments

Plant uptake experiments were conducted in a climate chamber using artificial sunlight. The temperature was 24 °C during daytime (14 h) and 20 °C during night (10 h). A small proportion of the Finnish soil was spiked with a mixture of the 17 pharmaceuticals in ACN. After approximately four hours of drying, the spiked soil was mixed with fresh Finnish soil and Finnish soil amended with OG2 to create **FS** and **FO**, respectively. The initial concentration was 500 ng/g for each pharmaceutical, and the BBF was added to reach a 1 % mass percentage of BBF (equal to 1–5 years of usage; <https://www.oegro.dk>). This spiking level was chosen to avoid sorption-site saturation and phytotoxic effects, enabling measurable wheatgrass uptake without compromising plant growth. It also falls within the upper yet environmentally relevant range (ng/g) reported for agricultural soils (Camacho-Arévalo et al., 2021; Christou et al., 2017). Ten wheatgrass seeds were directly sowed in each pot containing 300 g of soil. The pots were prepared in four replicates. The soil water content was maintained at 70 % of the soil maximum water holding capacity on a daily basis by adding double distilled to compensate for evapotranspiration. The following groups were distinguished: 1) a blank wheatgrass-free group (pharmaceuticals-free soil and amended soil); 2) a blank plant group (pharmaceuticals-free soil with wheatgrass and amended soil with wheatgrass); 3) a wheatgrass-free spiked soil group (spiked soil group and spiked amended soil group); and 4) a spiked plant-soil group (spiked plant-soil group and spiked amended plant-soil group)

In the plant-soil groups, wheatgrass plants were sampled at the mature stage (14 days). The harvested wheatgrass plants were thoroughly rinsed with double distilled water to remove attached soil particles, freeze dried, and separated into roots and leaves. Plant samples were weighed and cut into small pieces and ground into fine powders. At the same time, triplicate soil samples were collected from each soil-plant pot to analyze the pharmaceuticals present in bulk soil in each pot as well as in their SPW.

In the plant free-soil groups, soil samples were collected for a period of 45 days in triplicates. The samples were taken at 0, 1, 4, 7, 14, 28, and 45 days. The TES and SPW were collected at each interval.

2.3. Extraction method

An ultrasonication assisted extraction method was used, modified from Dong et al. (Dong et al., 2023) to obtain the total concentration in soil, denoted as the total extractable fraction (TES) in soil and amended soil, achieving satisfactory recovery rates between 57 % and 108 %, as detailed in Table S4. The extraction procedure consisted of the following steps: 5 g of soil were freeze-dried and sieved using a 2 mm mesh sieve, the sieved soil was then placed in a 50 ml centrifuge tube, and an IS was added and allowed to dry. Subsequently, 10 ml of ACN containing 2.5 % formic acid was added to the tube. The mixture was then shaken vigorously by hand and vortex-mixed for 30 s. The samples were ultrasonicated for 15 min, after which the extract was centrifuged at 2680 × g for 10 min at room temperature. The supernatant was decanted, and the soil was subjected to a second extraction with 10 ml of

ACN containing 2.5 % formic acid, followed by a third extraction using MeOH under identical conditions.

For extracting pharmaceuticals in plant roots and leaves, a similar method was employed. After spiking IS into the milled roots or leaves and drying, 10 ml of ACN with 2.5 % formic acid was added. The samples were hand-shaken, vortex-mixed, and ultrasonicated as before. Post-ultrasonication, the mixture was centrifuged, and the supernatant was replaced twice with 5 ml of the same ACN solution for further extraction. The final combined organic extracts were filtered through a 0.22 μm polypropylene filter and diluted with ultrapure water for analysis.

A sample of 20 g of wet soil was placed into a tube insert with a maxi spin filter of 0.22 μm pore size. The special tubes were then centrifuged at $1580 \times g$ for 30 min to separate SPW. This setting was selected to limit colloid mobilization, obtain sufficient SPW volume, and remain within the mechanical tolerance of the insert-membrane assembly. The collected pore water samples were spiked with IS and stored at -20°C until analysis.

2.4. LC-MS/MS analysis

The target screening and quantification method followed the procedure described by Narain-Ford et al. and Albergamo et al. (Albergamo et al., 2018; Narain-Ford et al., 2022).

To assess the accuracy and precision of the method, the selectivity, the recovery (via spiked recovery experiments (SRE)), the matrix effect (ME), the linearity of the calibration curves, the method limit of detection (MLOD), and the method limit of quantification (MLOQ) were evaluated (see Tables S2–S4). Internal calibration curves were constructed for analytes with available 13 C labeled/deuterated IS for accurate quantification (Table S1). Matrix matched calibration external curves were constructed for analytes without matching IS for six analytes in the range of 0.05–50 ng/g. A spiked recovery experiment was conducted at a concentration of 500 ng/g in soil in triplicates and 100 ng/g in wheatgrass root and leaf in triplicates. The recovery was in the range of 57–105 % in FS, 61–106 % in FO, 51–101 % in roots, and 62–99 % in leaves. A quality control sample, consisting of blank matrix to which IS was added only after extraction, was used to check for possible background concentrations of analytes. The recovery, which also represents accuracy, was calculated by comparing the concentration difference in extracted samples with and without added internal standards to the concentration of the added standards in the matrix extract. The precision was calculated as relative standard deviation (RSD) for each concentration level. ME (matrix effect) was calculated using triplicates with the following equation: $\text{ME} (\%) = 100 \times ((\text{concentration in spiked matrix} - \text{concentration in blank matrix}) / (\text{concentration in spiked blank} - 1))$. The MLOD and MLOQ were estimated from the ratio of the standard deviation of the response and the slope of the calibration curve of each extract.

2.5. Data processing

For the calculation of TES, a single first-order degradation model (Eq. (1)) was applied using Origin 2021 Pro.

$$C_t = C_0 \times \exp(-k \times t) \quad (1)$$

where C_t (ng/g) is the concentration at time t (day) in soil, C_0 is the initial concentration at $t = 0$, and k (day^{-1}) is the first-order degradation rate constant.

In this study, we calculated the solid-water distribution coefficient of pharmaceuticals (K_d) via Eq.(2), where C_s (ng/g) is the concentration in soil, and C_{spw} (ng/ml) is the concentration in SPW.

$$K_d = C_s / C_{\text{spw}} \quad (2)$$

In the plant-soil group, the bioaccumulation concentration factor

based on soil (BCF_s , g/g) and the bioaccumulation concentration factor based on soil pore water (BCF_{spw} , ml/g) were calculated on the basis of Eqs. (3) and (4) respectively, where C_p (ng/g) is the bioaccumulation concentration in whole wheatgrass (Carter et al., 2014). The linear model relating BCF_{spw} to half-life and K_d is given in Eq. (5), where a is the coefficient with respect to half-life (ml/g/day), b is the coefficient with respect to K_d (dimensionless), and c is the intercept (ml/g).

$$\text{BCF}_s = C_p / C_s \quad (3)$$

$$\text{BCF}_{\text{spw}} = C_p / C_{\text{spw}} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{BCF}_{\text{spw}} = a \times \text{half-life} + b \times K_d + c \quad (5)$$

3. Results and discussion

3.1. The degradation of pharmaceuticals in the wheatgrass-free soil and wheatgrass-free amended soil

3.1.1. The degradation of pharmaceuticals in the wheatgrass-free soil

The degradation of the studied pharmaceuticals in the wheatgrass-free soil (FS) and the wheatgrass-free amended soil (FO) is indicated by their half-lives ($t_{1/2}$), as presented in Table 1. Furthermore, in Table 2, the K_d values are shown for the pharmaceuticals in both the wheatgrass-free FS and FO groups, as well as in the wheatgrass FS and FO groups. The tested pharmaceuticals showed varying degradation half-lives ranging from 3.0 to 54.1 days in the wheatgrass-free FS group (Table 1). The compounds followed a first-order degradation model, with R^2 between 0.85 and 0.99 (Table 1). Carbamazepine exhibited a relatively high half-life of 54.1 days in the wheatgrass-free FS group (Table 1). These findings confirm its persistent nature, consistent with prior studies (Al-Rajab et al., 2015; Shao et al., 2018). In contrast, compounds such as ibuprofen, salicylic acid, and acetaminophen degraded rapidly, each displaying a half-life of approximately three days in the wheatgrass-free FS group (Table 1), which aligned with greenhouse pot experiments showing their quick degradation in plant-free soil in previous studies (Biel-Maeso et al., 2019; Thelusmond et al., 2018).

3.1.2. The degradation of pharmaceuticals in the wheatgrass-free amended soil

The application of a BBF influenced both the half-life and K_d values of pharmaceuticals in soil. The half-lives extended to between 5.1 and 59.0 days in the wheatgrass-free FO group (Table 1) compared to half-lives of 3.0–54.1 days in the wheatgrass-free FS group (Table 1), thereby potentially increasing the duration of pharmaceutical exposure to wheatgrass roots in FO and, thus, the potential for bioaccumulation. Simultaneously, there was an elevation in average K_d values (1.8–52.1 ml/g) in the wheatgrass FO group (Table 2) compared to the K_d values in the wheatgrass FS group (1.1–23.4 ml/g). According to Eq. (2), higher K_d implies lower freely dissolved concentrations in SPW, the root-accessible fraction. Therefore, BBF amendment reduced the bioavailability of the studied pharmaceuticals in soil, consequently decreasing their potential for bioaccumulation. Similar results have been found in other studies where the addition of organic fertilizers resulted in extended half-lives and increased adsorption values for pharmaceuticals in soil (Li et al., 2020; Mercl et al., 2021).

FS: Finnish soil; FO: Finnish soil amended with a bio-based fertilizer; $t_{1/2}$: half-life, day; k : degradation rate, day^{-1}

The concentrations of the pharmaceuticals in bulk soil on day 14 in the wheatgrass-free soil group and the wheatgrass-free amended soil group showed no significant ($p > 0.05$) difference to the concentrations in the wheatgrass soil group and the wheatgrass amended soil group, respectively (Table S7). Therefore, it is unlikely that the presence of wheatgrass significantly affects the chemical dissipation in the plant FS and FO groups, which aligns with the study that also found that plant

Table 1
Degradation parameters of pharmaceuticals in wheatgrass-free *FS* and wheatgrass-free *FO*.

Analytes	<i>FS</i>			<i>FO</i>		
	$t_{1/2} \pm \text{RSD}$, day	k , day ⁻¹	R ²	$t_{1/2} \pm \text{RSD}$, day	k , day ⁻¹	R ²
Bezafibrate	8.1 ± 0.82	0.086	0.98	11.0 ± 1.01	0.063	0.91
Carbamazepine	54.1 ± 3.22	0.013	0.85	59.0 ± 2.31	0.012	0.83
Ketoprofen	9.4 ± 0.81	0.074	0.94	11.2 ± 1.42	0.062	0.94
Metoprolol	23.0 ± 1.92	0.030	0.94	31.0 ± 1.42	0.022	0.93
Sulfamethoxazole	12.0 ± 1.92	0.058	0.97	8.3 ± 0.29	0.083	0.92
Trimethoprim	34.9 ± 1.41	0.020	0.91	39.3 ± 1.99	0.018	0.91
Caffeine	11.9 ± 3.41	0.058	0.95	18.7 ± 2.81	0.037	0.97
Antipyrine	19.3 ± 0.42	0.036	0.93	25.7 ± 2.39	0.027	0.92
Atenolol	7.0 ± 0.10	0.099	0.92	14.7 ± 2.30	0.047	0.93
Acetaminophen	3.0 ± 0.10	0.231	0.91	5.9 ± 1.22	0.117	0.94
Lincomycin	18.2 ± 1.82	0.039	0.91	28.5 ± 1.19	0.024	0.98
Naproxen	24.0 ± 2.61	0.029	0.97	34.7 ± 1.39	0.020	0.96
Tramadol	30.1 ± 1.22	0.023	0.98	40.8 ± 1.92	0.017	0.94
Diclofenac	12.7 ± 0.98	0.055	0.90	16.4 ± 1.12	0.042	0.95
Furosemide	10.5 ± 0.12	0.066	0.89	13.6 ± 1.82	0.051	0.92
Salicylic acid	3.2 ± 0.12	0.220	0.93	5.1 ± 1.32	0.136	0.92
Ibuprofen	3.4 ± 0.22	0.204	0.99	5.8 ± 1.10	0.119	0.95

Table 2
 K_d values in *FS* and *FO* in wheatgrass-free soil and wheatgrass soil, ml/g.

Analytes	Wheatgrass-free soil group ^a		Wheatgrass soil group ^b	
	<i>FS</i>	<i>FO</i>	<i>FS</i>	<i>FO</i>
Bezafibrate	2.7(4.3–10.5)	6.6(5.6–9.2)	2.9(0.4)	5.1(0.8)
Carbamazepine	3.6(2.6–9.0)	13.2(10.1–14.2)	3.9(1.3)	6.3(1.2)
Ketoprofen	3.8(3.0–5.2)	4.8(3.1–7.9)	4.9(2.6)	8.3(3.4)
Metoprolol	25.7(18.3–34.1)	31.5(28.1–47.9)	9.2(1.1)	12.5(1.8)
Sulfamethoxazole	4.8(2.3–9.4)	8.6(7.0–10.3)	2.2(0.8)	4.2(1.4)
Trimethoprim	23.5(20.1–36.3)	52.1(38.2–72.1)	8.0(1.4)	11.3(1.3)
Caffeine	8.9(6.3–12.2)	13.7(9.5–21.0)	6.1(0.9)	12.5(0.5)
Antipyrine	1.5(0.1–2.2)	2.2(0.3–3.0)	2.2(0.5)	5.9(1.2)
Atenolol	1.8(0.5–3.0)	2.3(1.0–4.2)	3.2(1.3)	8.1(1.1)
Acetaminophen	1.1(0.1–2.7)	1.8(0.9–3.4)	-	-
Lincomycin	2.6(0.6–3.2)	3.4(0.8–5.1)	3.3(1.4)	6.2(1.2)
Naproxen	5.4(3.1–9.6)	12.8(8.6–22.6)	6.3(1.0)	9.5(2.2)
Tramadol	6.8(2.6–9.1)	10.4(2.5–21.3)	4.8(1.4)	7.9(2.5)
Diclofenac	4.8(1.3–6.3)	6.9(1.6–7.2)	4.6(1.8)	6.9(1.5)
Furosemide	6.2(3.1–12.2)	9.4(8.5–20.7)	2.1(1.9)	4.3(0.9)
Salicylic acid	4.5(2.2–12.4)	7.9(5.6–20.8)	1.5(1.5)	3.1(0.5)
Ibuprofen	3.2(1.6–13.4)	6.3(3.4–25.2)	-	-

-: concentration in soil pore water is below MLOQ

^a K_d values are expressed in the average range in 45 days

^b K_d values are expressed in mean and RSD;

cultivation has a minimal effect on the degradation of pharmaceuticals (Carter et al., 2014) although some plants have been found to influence the dissipation of organic pollutants in remediation experiments (Nguyen et al., 2019). Therefore, observing the fate of pharmaceuticals in the wheatgrass-free soil group can help understand their uptake in the wheatgrass soil and wheatgrass amended soil experiments.

3.2. The bioaccumulation of pharmaceuticals by wheatgrass in the Finnish soil and the amended Finnish soil

3.2.1. The bioaccumulation of pharmaceuticals in wheatgrass grown in *FS*

The bioaccumulation concentration of studied pharmaceuticals in the wheatgrass *FS* group is shown in Fig. 1. Analysis of the wheatgrass from the wheatgrass-*FS* group showed the presence of 15 out of the 17 spiked compounds, with concentrations ranging from lowest detectable levels of 165 ng/g to a maximum of 1533 ng/g for carbamazepine (Fig. 1). Caffeine was measured at a concentration level of 320 ng/g in this study, which is in line with findings of caffeine at concentrations ranging from hundreds to thousands of ng/g in various crops under greenhouse conditions (Li et al., 2022) (Hurtado et al., 2017; Li et al., 2020). Its lipophilicity is lower than that of carbamazepine, with a log P

of -0.1 , and it is naturally present in *FS* (Table S1). Furthermore, acetaminophen, which is also naturally present in *FS*, has higher log P and log D values than caffeine and carbamazepine. However, its accumulation level in wheatgrass was below MLOD in this study (Fig. 1). Similar findings were observed in other studies involving cucumbers and peppers, indicating a trend of a low bioaccumulation level across different plant species (Boxall et al., 2006; Wu et al., 2013). This indicates that the lipophilicity (such as log P) alone cannot predict uptake capacity in our study. Carter et al. (2014) consider the degradation to be the primary fate of most pharmaceuticals in soil-plant system. Consistent with this, previous studies, including greenhouse trials with wheat and soybean and constructed-wetland experiments, reported ibuprofen to be below MLOD in plant tissues, with removal attributed mainly to microbial degradation rather than plant accumulation (Cortés et al., 2013; Zhang et al., 2016). In our study, acetaminophen and ibuprofen exhibited short half-lives (3.0 and 3.4 days, respectively; Table 1); thus, bioavailability decreased quickly, likely precluding measurable uptake by wheatgrass before substantial degradation had occurred. Carbamazepine exhibits a longer half-life in the wheatgrass-free *FS* group (Table 1) and lower K_d values in the wheatgrass *FS* group (3.6 ml/g), as noted in Table 2. The relatively lower dissipation rates and K_d values resulted in the highest observed concentration of carbamazepine in SPW, reaching 79.4 ng/ml in the wheatgrass *FS* group. These factors contribute to the accumulation of carbamazepine in wheatgrass to levels as high as 1533 ng/g, which was in line with a study showing that carbamazepine exhibited considerable bioaccumulation in crops (Beltrán et al., 2020). The observed half-life of caffeine was 11.9 days (Table 1), with moderate K_d values of 6.1 ml/g (Table 2), leading to a measured concentration of 320 ng/g in wheatgrass, which is lower than that of carbamazepine. These observations highlight the influence of persistence in soil and the adsorption affinity of pharmaceuticals on their uptake by wheatgrass.

3.2.2. The bioaccumulation of pharmaceuticals in wheatgrass grown in *FO*

The initial concentrations in bulk soil for each compound on day 0 showed no significant differences between the unamended wheatgrass *FS* group and the BBF amended wheatgrass *FO* group ($p > 0.05$) (Table S7), indicating that the variations observed in wheatgrass grown under *FS* and *FO* conditions cannot be attributed into differences initial added standard concentrations. The concentrations of the studied compounds in the wheatgrass-*FO* group ranged from 165 to 900 ng/g, showing a reduction compared to the 273–1533 ng/g observed in the wheatgrass *FS* group (Fig. 1). Carbamazepine showed the highest concentration at 900 ng/g, while salicylic acid had the lowest concentration at 165 ng/g in wheatgrass in *FO* (Fig. 1). Noteworthy, ibuprofen and

Fig. 1. Concentrations in wheatgrass grown on soils from the plant-*FS* and plant-*FO* groups. *FS*: Finnish soil; *FO*: Amended Finnish soil with a BBF; data for ibuprofen and acetaminophen was below the method limit of quantification; error bars depict RSD.

acetaminophen were detected at levels below the MLOD. These findings suggest that the application of the BBF reduces the bioaccumulation of those pharmaceuticals in wheatgrass and that this effect is not counterbalanced by the extension of the half-life of the components caused by the presence of the BBF. These results align with the outcomes of studies on the application of biochar or biosolids to reduce the bioaccumulation of pharmaceuticals by enhancing their sorption to soil (Fu et al., 2016; Li et al., 2020).

3.3. The influence of BBF on uptake capacity of pharmaceuticals by wheatgrass in soil

3.3.1. The bioaccumulation concentration factors in wheatgrass in *FS* and *FO*

The uptake concentration factors (BCF_s and BCF_{spw}) were calculated to better understand the bioaccumulation capacity of the studied pharmaceuticals in wheatgrass grown in *FS* and *FO* and are shown in Table 3. The values of BCF_s ranged from 1.7 to 12.4 g/g, while BCF_{spw} ranged from 9.5 to 19.6 ml/g (Table 3). Salicylic acid exhibited the highest BCF_s at 12.4 g/g, and carbamazepine had the highest BCF_{spw} at 19.6 ml/g in *FS* (Table 3). Metoprolol had the lowest BCF_s at 1.7 g/g, and caffeine had the lowest BCF_{spw} at 9.5 ml/g. The BCF_s and BCF_{spw} could not be obtained for acetaminophen and ibuprofen as their concentration in wheatgrass in *FS* was below the MLOQ (Table 3). We observed that values for BCF_{spw} were consistently higher than those for BCF_s in the wheatgrass *FS* group, indicating that the concentration of pharmaceuticals in soil pore water provides a more accurate measure of bioaccumulation than the concentration of pharmaceuticals adsorbed onto soil solids. This finding is consistent with another study, which found that higher root concentration factors based on soil pore water (RCF_{spw}), compared to soil-based RCF_s , may be attributed to the reduced bioavailability of soil-sorbed pharmaceuticals for radish root uptake relative to those present in soil pore water (Li et al., 2019). This observation underscores the importance of considering the

Table 3

BCF_s (g/g) and BCF_{spw} (ml/g) values in *FS* and *FO* in plant group.

Analytes	<i>FS</i>		<i>FO</i>		$ \Delta K_d/\Delta t_{1/2} $
	BCF_s	BCF_{spw}	BCF_s	BCF_{spw}	
Bezafibrate	4.0	12.1	1.8	11.7	1.1
Carbamazepine	4.8	19.6	2.0	18.6	1.1
Ketoprofen	2.8	13.9	1.2	13.2	4.1
Metoprolol	1.7	15.2	0.8	10.9	1.0
Sulfamethoxazole	7.4	16.2	2.4	15.2	1.1
Trimethoprim	1.9	15.3	1.3	11.2	1.0
Caffeine	1.6	9.5	0.9	8.7	0.5
Antipyrine	8.7	19.1	3.4	17.1	0.6
Atenolol	4.7	15.3	2.7	12.3	0.5
Acetaminophen	-	-	-	-	-
Lincomycin	5.4	17.8	2.3	14.2	0.5
Naproxen	2.4	15.0	1.4	13.3	0.3
Tramadol	3.1	14.8	1.7	12.1	0.4
Diclofenac	3.9	17.9	1.7	16.3	1.2
Furosemide	8.1	16.8	2.1	15.8	1.4
Salicylic acid	12.4	18.6	4.2	17.2	1.3
Ibuprofen	-	-	-	-	-

concentration of pharmaceuticals in soil pore water when assessing their uptake potential in wheatgrass.

3.3.2. The correlation of BCF_{spw} with half-life and K_d in *FS*

The correlation between $\log P$ or $\log D$ and BCF_{spw} for the pharmaceuticals studied was minimal, evidenced by low correlation coefficients ($R^2 < 0.10$) (Figure S1 and S2), in line with the poor relationship found in similar studies (Li et al., 2019; Miller et al., 2016). We expect that temporal changes in SPW concentrations are related to plant root uptake of pharmaceuticals. Given that compound dynamics in SPW are primarily driven by degradation and sorption according to the equation, $C_{spw} = C_s/K_d$, where C_{spw} is concentration in soil pore water; C_s :

concentration in soil, it enables exploring of the relationships between half-life as well as K_d values (Table 2) and BCF_{spw} (Table 3). The linear model was fitted for compounds divided by their half-life (Eq.(5)). Those with a long half-life (over 14 days): $BCF_{spw} = 0.005 \times \text{half-life} - 0.0172 \times K_d + 1.2948$, with $R^2 = 0.70$ and those with a short half-life (less than 14 days): $BCF_{spw} = 0.0032 \times \text{half-life} - 0.047 \times K_d + 1.3409$, with $R^2 = 0.73$ (Figure S3). For the compounds with a long half-life, we observed the coefficient half-life of 0.005 (ml/g/day) and K_d of -0.0172 . The coefficients indicate that although the half-life of compounds still positively influences uptake, the impact of their K_d values becomes more significant

BCF_s : bioaccumulation concentration factor based on soil; BCF_{spw} : bioaccumulation concentration factor based on soil pore water; **FS**: Finnish soil; **FO**: Finnish soil amended with BBF; -: the values cannot be calculated; $t_{1/2}$: half-life, day; K_d : soil-water distribution coefficient, ml/g; $|\Delta K_d / \Delta t_{1/2}|$: the absolute ratio values of difference in K_d and $t_{1/2}$ between in **FS** and **FO**

for compounds with short half-lives. The observed coefficient values for half-life (0.003 ml/g/day) and K_d (-0.047) followed this trend for compounds with short half-lives. Moreover, the coefficient ratios of K_d to half-life were 3.4 and 14.7 (g/ml) day for compounds with long and short half-lives, respectively. Predominantly, the studied compounds enter plant cells via passive transport at the beginning of exposure (Miller et al., 2016; Nason et al., 2019), driven by concentration gradients between the root and SPW and generally more efficient than energy-requiring active transport (Colon and Toor, 2016). Accordingly, early-time uptake is constrained by sorption-limited bioavailability, higher K_d lowers C_{spw} and weakens the gradient-driven influx across compounds. As exposure proceeds, root concentrations increase while C_{spw} declines due to dissipation; the transmembrane gradient diminishes and passive flux wanes. Under these lower-gradient conditions, particularly for compounds with longer half-lives in this study (>14 days), any further net accumulation may become relatively more influenced by non-diffusive processes (e.g., carrier- or energy-mediated transport), although sorption remains an important control. This is consistent with our regression results: the coefficient ratio 14.7 (g/ml)-day for short-lived compounds that was higher compared to 3.4 (g/ml)-day for longer-lived compounds in soil.

To assess the generalizability of our proposed linear model framework, we explored linear relationships correlating BCF_{spw} with half-life and K_d values as reported in other studies (Li et al., 2020, 2019). We utilized data from the study that included BCF_{spw} , half-life, and K_d values for radish, establishing a similar linear relationship and demonstrating R^2 values ranging from 0.80 to 0.83 across 28- and 35-day greenhouse experiments with varied soil water contents (Table S8) (Li et al., 2019). Another study provided data that revealed higher R^2 values of 0.83 for the relationship between BCF_{spw} and half-life and K_d (Table S8) (Li et al., 2020). These results establish a robust linear relationship between concentration factors and parameters, including half-life and K_d values, yielding a higher R^2 value compared to models based solely on log P or log D (Li et al., 2019). This supports the validity of observing the behavior of compounds in SPW to demonstrate the uptake capacity of pharmaceuticals in various crops.

3.3.3. The correlation of BCF_{spw} with half-life and K_d in FO

The BCF_s varied from 0.8 to 4.2 g/g in **FO**, which are lower than those calculated in **FS** as outlined in Table 3. BCF_{spw} ranged from 8.7 to 18.6 ml/g in **FO**, which is lower than those in **FS**, with caffeine showing the lowest BCF_{spw} at 8.7 ml/g and carbamazepine the highest at 18.6 ml/g. This indicates that the addition of BBF decreased the uptake potential for the studied compounds in wheatgrass in this study. The coefficient ratios of K_d to half-life in **FS** are 3.4 and 14.7 (g/ml)-day for compounds with long and short half-lives, respectively, as discussed in Section 3.2. This implies that if the absolute ratios of difference in K_d /difference in half-life exceed or are lower than 0.3 (1/3.4) and 0.07 (1/

14.7) for compounds with long and short half-lives, respectively, their BCF_{spw} values could change. As outlined in Table 3, the absolute ratio values of the differences in half-life and K_d between **FS** and **FO** range from 0.3 to 1.1 for compounds with long half-lives and from 0.5 to 4.1 for those with short half-lives. These results align with the observed reduction in RCF_{spw} in **FO**, indicating a decreased bioaccumulation potential due to the presence of a BBF in the soil.

3.3.4. Food safety assessment in soil and a BBF-amended soil

Because most target compounds are not registered crop pesticides and thus lack plant-food maximum residue limits (MRLs), we evaluated food-safety using a screening dietary risk metric. Body-weight-normalized exposure (EDI, estimated daily intake) was estimated on a dry-weight basis (leaf) as $EDI = C_{dw} \times IR / BW$, where C_{dw} is the residue concentration in leaf (Figure S4), IR is the intake rate (6 g/day), and BW is body weight (60 kg). We then computed hazard quotient $HQ = EDI / \text{reference value}$ as shown in Table 4. Across all analytes, HQs were $\ll 1$ (Table 4). The highest value was observed for carbamazepine ($HQ = 0.081$ in **FS**, 0.044 in **FO**), while most others were ≤ 0.016 and likewise decreased in the BBF-amended soil, for example, atenolol declined from 0.010 to 0.006. These findings indicate a low screening-level dietary risk under the assessed consumption scenario. Moreover, BBF amendment consistently reduced HQs, consistent with diminished plant uptake and/or bioavailability. Therefore, BBF use appears protective by further lowering potential dietary exposure.

4. Conclusion

This study investigated the influence of the application of a BBF on the uptake of pharmaceuticals from soil through greenhouse experiments with wheatgrass, focusing on 17 spiked pharmaceuticals. For the first time, a notable linear relationship was established between BCF_{spw} and key parameters such as K_d and half-life, enhancing the predictability of ionized pharmaceuticals. The addition of BBF was found to increase both the adsorption and persistence of pharmaceuticals in soil; however, the effect on bioaccumulation was more pronounced due to increased adsorption than increased persistence. Consequently, BCF_{spw} values were reduced in **FO** compared to **FS**. Reducing the bioaccumulation of

Table 4

Hazard quotients (HQ, unitless) for studied pharmaceuticals in edible wheatgrass (leaf) grown on Finnish soil (**FS**) and a BBF-amended Finnish soil (**FO**).

Analytes	HQ × 100 in FS	HQ × 100 in FO	ADI, ng/g bw/day
Antipyrine	2.7	1.9	1.5 ^a
Atenolol	1.0	0.6	1.5 ^a
Bezafibrate	0.4	0.3	1.5 ^a
Caffeine	0.7	0.4	1.5 ^a
Carbamazepine	8.1	4.4	1.5 ^a
Ketoprofen	0.0	0.0	1.5 ^a
Lincomycin	0.1	0.0	30 ^b
Metoprolol	0.9	0.8	1.5 ^a
Sulfamethoxazole	0.0	0.0	50 ^c
Tramadol	1.1	0.9	1.5 ^a
Trimethoprim	0.2	0.1	4.2 ^d
Diclofenac	1.6	0.6	0.5 ^e
Furosemide	0.5	0.0	1.5 ^a
Salicylic acid	0.7	0.5	1.5 ^a

a, Threshold of toxicological concern (Cramer class III) applied where no substance-specific ADI exists (EFSA Scientific Committee, 2019); b, microbiological ADI set on the intestinal microbiological endpoint (Joint FAO/WHO Expert Committee on Food Additives, JECFA); c, group ADI for sulfonamides used as a conservative benchmark (JECFA); d, lower (microbiological) ADI used for consumer risk (European Medicines Agency (EMA)); e, human-health ADI used for benchmarking (EU/technical files); HQ was calculated as $HQ = EDI / \text{Reference value}$ or ADI, with EDI = the residue concentration in leaf (dry weight, Figure S4) × IR (intake rate, 6 g/day) / BW (body weight, 60 kg); ADI, acceptable daily intake. The compounds are now shown represent the values are zero.

pharmaceuticals in wheatgrass through enhanced adsorption is indeed an effective strategy. The BBF application reduced the corresponding hazard quotients (HQs), indicating a protective effect that mitigates potential dietary risk. However, the scope of this study is limited to a single soil type and plant species. Additionally, a single linear model cannot fully capture mechanistic differences among compounds; future work should validate the framework on larger datasets, across additional soils and plant species, and with broader compound characteristics, and should explore interactions that better reflect underlying processes.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Yan Dong: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Eva de Rijke:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **J. Chris Slootweg:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Boris Jansen:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgement

This work was supported by European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (grant agreement No. 818309 (www.lex4bio.eu)) and the China Scholarship Council (CSC) (grant numbers 202008320285). The authors are solely responsible for the content of this study, which does not necessarily represent the views of the European Union. We also thank Patricia Aquilar and Rick Helmus of the Institute for Biodiversity and Ecosystem for their lab support.

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.ecoenv.2025.119313](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2025.119313).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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